

Service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking industry: an empirical study in Vietnam

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Service quality and customer satisfaction play a vital role in any business. But it is particularly important in emerging markets such as Vietnam which still needs to catch up with western service standards. It is even more important in service industry as it deals with people. Further, local businesses need to compete with foreign businesses due to the Foreign Direct Investments in Vietnam. In this context, the purpose of the article is to test the impact of the five dimensions—*tangibility*, *responsiveness*, *reliability*, *assurance* and *empathy*—of the SERVQUAL on customer satisfaction in Vietnamese banking industry. Results of the study indicate that all the five dimensions of service quality significantly impact customer satisfaction. More specifically, *Reliability* and *Empathy* most influence the customer satisfaction.

Keywords: banking industry, consumer satisfaction, service quality, SERVQUAL, Vietnam

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Introduction

In the competitive banking industry, the survival and growth of a bank is determined via the delivery of service quality to clients, and financial organizations are equipped with a different kind of financial products and services (Hinson, Mohammed & Mensah 2006, Samli & Frohlich 1992). Customer satisfaction is a key factor to successfully build a potential and loyal customer system, and quality of provided service is a main contributor to the success of banks (Idrees & Xinping 2017). According to Parasuraman et al. (1985), service quality was the global assessment of the overall quality of service. Service quality was also considered an abstract theory. There was no agreement on conceptualizing service quality and various authors concentrated on multiple aspects of service quality. Nevertheless, it provided managers with a tool to research service quality concepts to identify quality and enhance the quality-of-service of companies to achieve customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction has many definitions and concepts. Customer satisfaction was defined as to what extent customer needs, expectations and wishes regarding the services and products are accomplished for long-term business success (Ardakani, Ardakani & Ardakani 2015). Consumers were focused on receiving competitive benefits (Mozaheb, Alamolhodei &

Fotouchi 2015) and the long-lasting success aspect for a company's competitiveness (Garver & Gagnon 2002, Jamal & Naser 2002). So, customer satisfaction became a vital factor for the companies that delivered the services online (Ankit 2011). Anderson and Sullivan (1993) also indicated that customer satisfaction was essential to the long-run reputation of firms.

In the banking industry, several researchers showed the significant impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in different developing countries and emerging markets (Ahmed 2017, Ali & Raza 2015, Sulieman 2013). SERVQUAL model, including Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance, and Empathy as dimensions of service quality, was used in these studies to examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. These five dimensions were found to have significant impact on customer satisfaction in most of the studies; however, some studies found no significant impact on some factors (Vencataya et al. 2019). Besides, most of these researches focused on a specific bank or a specific group of banks (such as Islamic banks) in a developing country; therefore, there is a lack of research on commercial banks. This study fills the gap in Vietnam.

In Vietnam, to satisfy the increasing demands of customers, investing and developing the best quality services is one of the top priority strategies of Vietnamese banks, especially Vietnamese commercial banks. The Vietnamese commercial banks have recently had outstanding progress in the capital, infrastructure quality, and technical information. According to Vietnam News (2020), some of Vietnam's commercial banks reap outstanding achievements through providing high-quality service, which conquered almost fastidious customers in Vietnam including Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade Vietnam (Vietcombank), Vietnam Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Industry and Trade (Vietinbank), Vietnam Technological and Commercial Joint Stock Bank (Techcombank), Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam (BIDV), Vietnam Prosperity Joint Stock Commercial Bank (VPBank), Military Commercial Joint Stock Bank (MBBank), Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (Agribank), Asia Commercial Joint Stock Bank (ACB), Tien Phong Commercial Joint Stock Bank (TPBank), Ho Chi Minh City Development Joint Stock Commercial Bank (HD Bank). However, the services provided were still not synchronous and did not create fundamental utilities to be exchanged for service users due to changes in business environment (Bui & Le 2019). Domestic commercial banks had to face increasing competition with not only current foreign banks but also potential European banks who would be able to access the Vietnamese market due to the European Union-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA). Therefore, banks need to recognize the pros and cons of the services provided and find the appropriate development steps suitable for themselves and assessing the quality of current banking services and customer satisfaction is a necessary job.

Several studies use SERVQUAL model to examine service quality and customer's satisfaction in Vietnamese banks (Nguyen et al. 2021, Tran, Nguyen & Chang 2015). These researches showed that all five dimensions—Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance, and Empathy—that have a significant impact on customer satisfaction and they also contributed that SERVQUAL model is applicable in Vietnam. Tran, Nguyen and Chang (2015) studied in Vietnam banking industry but the authors just focused on the quality of deposit services. Other studies were conducted in a specific bank or branch (Nguyen et al. 2021). Therefore, the purpose of the study is to research in a broader context of general service quality (not just deposit services) of Vietnamese commercial banks (not just a brand or branch) in order to see how service quality influences customer satisfaction. Specifically, the paper aims at answering the following research questions: What are the impacts of service quality on customer satisfaction in Vietnamese commercial banks? Which factor has the most influence? The answers may help bank managers increase customer satisfaction by improving service quality. In this paper, literature review is first presented, followed by conceptual framework, hypotheses development and methodology. Then results are described and analyzed for discussion and implications for managers.

Literature Review

Service Quality

Service quality has been studied by different researchers to examine perceptions of quality of service in the context of both tangible and intangible characteristics (Aldlaigan & Buttle 2002, Cronin & Taylor 1992, Parasuraman et al. 1988). The ordinary meaning that most authors agree with was proved by Parasuraman et al. (1988) when they evaluated service quality with the SERVQUAL model and described service quality as the size of the difference between the expectations and perception of customers. Parasuraman et al. (1988) depicted service quality as the distinction between the customer's expectations of service and the delivered factor. Five dimensions including Tangibility, Responsiveness, Reliability, Empathy, and Assurance were widely used to estimate service quality. This is the best model to measure service quality in the banking industry in different countries (Hussaien et al. 2020, Rijwani et al. 2017, Vencataya et al. 2019,). This is acceptable in the banking industry in which the service quality relies on the degree it satisfies the expectation or demands of customers (Tran & Nguyen 2020). Tran, Nguyen and Chang (2015) also argued that SERVQUAL model can be used to examine service quality of the whole system in banking industry and that it is important for Vietnamese banks to improve the quality of service to compete effectively.

The Relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

About the link between customer satisfaction and service quality, Oliver (1993) first proposed that service quality would exist earlier than customer satisfaction irrespective of whether these concepts were collective or transaction-specific. Some studies discovered practical support for the statement presented above (Wang & Shieh 2006), where customer satisfaction was based on an outcome of service quality. In connecting service quality and customer satisfaction, investigators had been more accurate about the definition and evaluations of satisfaction and service quality. Service quality and customer satisfaction had in common. However, satisfaction was typically a larger concept, while service quality concentrates particularly on service features (Wilson et al. 2008). Even though it was declared that other factors such as the price or quality of a product could impact customer satisfaction, made-out service quality was a part of customer satisfaction (Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler 2006). This concept was similar to the statement of Wilson et al. (2008) and proved by the conception of customer satisfaction submitted by other studies.

There were several studies on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in banking industry in different context, especially in developing countries. The quantitative methods and SERVQUAL model were used in most of these studies with Tangibility, Responsiveness, Reliability, Empathy, and Assurance as independent variables and customer satisfaction as the dependent variable. The results mostly showed that all the five dimensions had significant influence on customer satisfaction. Specifically, Suliman (2003) studied banking quality service in Jordanian context. Vencataya et al. (2019) examined Maritius banks and found that Empathy had the most influence on customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, studies of Felix (2017) in Rwanda, Magoma et al. (2019) in Tanzania, and Hussaien et al. (2020) in Sri Lanka showed that Reliability was the strongest factor that influences customer satisfaction toward service quality of banks. Rijwani et al. (2017) studied Indian banks and found that Assurance was the strongest factor. Besides, Ali and Raza (2017) studied Islamic banks in Pakistan and added *compliance* as a factor to the model. It also had the greatest positive influence on customer satisfaction, followed by responsiveness and other factors, whereas the results of Vencataya et al. (2019) reflected no significant impact of responsiveness on customer satisfaction towards service quality in banking industry. The mentioned studies focused on a specific bank (Sulimen 2013), or both public and private banks (Hussaien et al. 2020), quality of a specific bank service (Magoma 2019) or conducted in different context outside Vietnam. That is why this paper aims at finding which factors of service quality have significant impact and which factor has the most impact on customer satisfaction in Vietnamese commercial banks.

In the context of Vietnamese banks, some researchers also used SERVQUAL model to examine service quality and found that customer's satisfaction was positively influenced by the five dimensions. Results of Tran, Nguyen and Chang (2015) showed that Tangibility had the strongest influence while the greatest influence factor on customer satisfaction was Empathy in studies of Tran and Nguyen (2020) and Nguyen et al. (2021). Tran, Nguyen and Chang (2015) also studied Vietnamese commercial banks, but in Hanoi city and there were only 150 respondents participated in this study, and the authors just focused on the quality of deposit services, whereas study of Tran and Nguyen (2020) was conducted in a branch of Techcombank and Nguyen et al. (2021) examined a specific bank (Bac A bank). Therefore, this study is attempting to research a broader context of service quality of Vietnamese commercial banks.

The Conceptual Framework

The SERVQUAL model is considered the best model to measure service quality since the five scales embrace service quality (Wilson et al. 2008). As illustrated in the research question, a question has been concerned about the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction. To find the answer to this question, the SERVQUAL model is used to evaluate customer satisfaction. Ladhari (2009) recommends using the SERVQUAL model because it is the best scale to utilize when estimating the quality of service in particularly diverse industries. In addition, the SERVQUAL model is also fitting to select the most significant factor of this model that suits specific service being estimated to ensure reliable and valid outcomes. In this study, the model below tests the effect of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework

Source: Parasuraman et al. (1988)

Figure 1 shows that the five dimensions of service quality have a connection with customer satisfaction. Suppose customers feel satisfied with the service quality. In that case, these service quality dimensions will have a strong relationships with customer satisfaction. Then, a relationship can be determined between service quality and customer satisfaction. This model is adequate to the demand of this research. Each dimension refers to customers' feelings, reflecting the level of satisfaction from customers' perceptions. Banks' customers are the people who focus exceptionally on services, such as the attitude of the staff or the speed of the bank's response to their requirements. It is shown to be reliable in the context of Vietnamese banks (Nguyen et al. 2021, Tran Nguyen & Chang 2015, Tran & Nguyen 2020).

Hypotheses Development

The connection between customer satisfaction and service quality in Sweden banking is analyzed and it is

found that combining tangible and intangible components of high quality in provided services and products may form long-term association with their clients (Zineldin 2005). As mentioned above, SERVQUAL model with five dimensions of service quality were widely used in general and in banking industry in particular.

Parasuraman et al. (1985) defined tangibility as the image of the equipment, machines, behavior of staffs, manuals, materials, and information systems of the bank. Similarly, tangibility relates to the physical facility, personnel, and communication materials on customers (Sureshchandar, Rajendran & Anantharaman 2001). Scholars have found significant impact of tangibles on customer satisfaction in banking industry (Felix 2017, Magoma et al. 2019). In the study of Tran, Nguyen & Chang (2015) in Vietnam, tangibles had the strongest impact on the customer satisfaction. Interestingly, it was found that Tangibles had no significant impact on customer satisfaction in study of Khan and Fasih (2014) in Pakistan. In this study, the authors hypothesize that the Tangibles significantly affect customer satisfaction in the Vietnam banking context. Our first hypothesis is:

H1. Tangibles have a positive influence on customer satisfaction.

Responsiveness, which helps quickly estimate the ability to deal with the problem soon, handles customers' complaints, supports clients, and satisfies the client's requirements (Parasuraman et al. 1988). When employees respond to the problems of customers, their satisfaction will increase (Pakurar et al. 2019). Responsiveness also impacted significantly customer satisfaction in banking industry (Lay & Marimuthu 2016). However, Munusamy et al. (2010) studied banking sector in Malaysia and showed that responsiveness had no significant effect on customer satisfaction. In Vietnam, a positive influence of responsiveness on customer satisfaction was also found in Bac A bank (Nguyen et al. 2021). Therefore, it was expected to have a positive influence of responsiveness on customer satisfaction of Vietnamese commercial banks in this study as responding or giving feedback to customers is important.

H2. Responsiveness has a positive influence on customer satisfaction.

Reliability represented the capability to supply services correctly and timely (Parasuraman et al. 1985). This factor depends on the stability in the application of services and respects commitments, and keeps promises to customers. It was proven that reliability strongly impacted customer satisfaction in banking industry in studies of previous authors such as Felix (2017), Vencataya et al. (2019). However, Sanjuq (2014) showed a negative relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction, but no significant impact. In Vietnam, reliability was proved to have a positive relationship with bank services and quality of Vietnamese commercial banks (Phan & Phan 2021). Thus, we wish to test if reliability influences customer satisfaction in Vietnam.

H3. Reliability has a positive influence on customer satisfaction.

Assurance refers to the safety that customers feel when using services or it is also about the protection customers from harm or risks (Tran 2018). In some countries, studies showed a significant impact of assurance on customer satisfaction in banking industry. Nevertheless, assurance did not have significant impact on customer satisfaction of banks in Saudi Arabia (Sanjuq 2014). In general, this factor plays an important role because it relates to the safety and financial resources of customers. The above studies in Vietnam showed a positive influence of reliability on customer satisfaction. So in this study, we formulate our next hypothesis to test a positive influence of assurance on customer satisfaction with banking services of Vietnamese commercial banks.

H4. Assurance has a positive influence on customer satisfaction.

Empathy is the thoughtful, sympathy and the best preparation for customers and raises belief in customers, which is proven from professional services, outstanding technical knowledge, attitude, politeness, and excellent communication skills when serving customers (Parasuraman 1988). Studies have shown that empathy significantly influenced customer satisfaction in banking industry. However, Munusamy, Cselliah & Hor (2010) found that empathy did not have significant impact on satisfying customers in Malaysia. In Vietnam, for customer satisfaction with deposit services, empathy had the greatest influence. In addition, as this factor can make customers believe in bank services, we develop next hypothesis to examine it in the context of Vietnamese commercial banks.

H5. Empathy has a positive influence on customer satisfaction

Methodology

Questionnaire Design

We used the SERVQUAL scale developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988). However, to fit the research objective of the study about the relationship between five service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction, the customer satisfaction scale was also added to the survey. In addition, the questionnaire based on Parasuraman's theory was rephrased to make it compatible with Vietnamese culture and to confirm its validity. All the survey questions were in the form of multiple-choice for personal information and close-ended questions to rate their experience, based on the constructed questions of Parasuraman et al. (1988), including four items for each of the five variables: Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance, and Empathy. The total measurements are 20. Questions about the five independent variables comprised of the questions from 1 to 20 (Nguyen et al. 2021, Parasuraman et al. 1988). For the inquiries related to dependent variables - Customer Satisfaction, the questions were about evaluating the level of satisfaction with overall services quality, assessing the level customer will continue using services, and measuring the level customer will introduce services Vietnam bank industry to other people. It is a 5-point Likert scale. More specifically, the respondents answered the questions by choosing the correct number that presents the size they agreed with an opinion. The scale used in the survey questions is from 1 to 5. These numbers were stated as number 1=very dissatisfied, 2=dissatisfied, 3=neutral, 4=satisfied, and 5=very satisfied.

Sample Characteristics

The sample was chosen from the customers of Techcombank, MB Bank, VP Bank, ACB, Vietcombank, Vietinbank, Agribank, BIDV, HD Bank, and TP Bank who have been using different bank services such as ATM, Internet banking, mobile banking, etc. Two hundred seventy questionnaires were given to selected banks' customers after meeting them in the lobby of those selected banks to collect data. We received 250 completed questionnaires. Most of the customers who responded to the surveys were between 46 and 65 accounted for 31%. Meanwhile, 26% of those were in the range of from 25 to 45 and over 65. Thirty-six percent of the respondents were male and 64% female. The academic level of respondents is almost equal among groups of high school (23%), Bachelor (25%), Master (26%) and others (25%). Seventy-four percent of them used services of Vietnamese commercial banks more than 50 times per month while customers who used less than 50 times accounted for 26%.

Reliability and Validity

The value of Cronbach's Alpha of all SERVQUAL dimensions confirmed to proceed with the Exploratory Factor Analysis. Tangibles has a Cronbach's alpha is .79. Considering the Responsiveness dimension, the

measure of the Responsiveness has an alpha of .74, which is elevated and can be applied to perform exploratory factor analysis. Moreover, Cronbach's alpha analysis results indicate that the Reliability, Empathy, and Assurance dimensions are .73, .86, and .86, respectively. Therefore, they are accepted for the next step of analysis. Further, for the factor analysis of the five dimensions, the results illustrate that KMO has a value of $.71 > .5$, making factor analysis acceptable. The cumulative total variance of the five dimensions is 64.20%, Bartlett's Sig. $< .05$, Eigenvalues > 1 , which meets EFA requirements (Hair et al. 2010). All the conditions are satisfied, so these 20 variables were kept for further tests.

Analysis and Results

Based on the regression coefficients in Table 1, Reliability has the highest impact on customer satisfaction with Standardized Beta coefficient = .37, followed by Empathy with Standardized Beta coefficient = .33, then Assurance and Tangibles with Standardized Beta coefficient in turn equal to .30 and .29, the lowest is Responsiveness with Standardized Beta coefficient = .27, $p < .05$. Therefore, all five dimensions have a positive impact on customer satisfaction. The results also present that the VIF coefficients of the independent variables are all less than 2, so there is no multicollinearity phenomenon between the independent variables. Adjusted $R^2 = .58$ indicates the appropriateness of the model. Durbin-Watson coefficient is 1.73.

Table 1. Regression Analysis

<i>Dependent Variable: CUS (Customer Satisfaction)</i>								
Model	Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
	(Constant)	-.16	.19		-.81	.41		
	TAN Tangibility	.24	.03	.29	6.98	.00	.93	1.07
	RES Responsiveness	.19	.03	.27	6.60	.00	.95	1.05
	REL Reliability	.18	.02	.37	9.16	.00	.98	1.02
	EMP Empathy	.24	.03	.33	8.06	.00	.96	1.04
	ASS Assurance	.18	.02	.30	7.33	.00	.94	1.05

H1 (accepted): Tangibles have a positive ($b = .29$, $p < .00$) influence on customer satisfaction. H2 (accepted): Responsiveness has a positive ($b = .27$, $p < .00$) influence on customer satisfaction. H3 (accepted): Reliability has a positive ($b = .37$, $p < .00$) influence on customer satisfaction. H4 (accepted): Assurance has a positive ($b = .30$, $p < .00$) influence on customer satisfaction. H5 (accepted) Empathy has a positive ($b = .33$, $p < .00$) relationship with customer satisfaction.

Discussion

Reliability has significant impact on customer satisfaction at Vietnamese commercial banks. This result is in line with previous researches of Marković and Janković (2013), and Rijiwani et al. (2017). Specially, Reliability has the strongest impact on customer satisfaction with standardized beta coefficient value of .37. However, the results contradict (Munusamy, Cselliah & Hor 2010, Sanjuq 2014). Besides, while researches of Tran and Nguyen (2020) in a branch and Nguyen et al. (2021) in a specific bank showed that Empathy was the strongest factor, in this research of broader context in Vietnam, Reliability has the greatest impact on customer satisfaction. Therefore, the result shows that customers in Vietnam paid much attention to accurate and timely banking services.

Empathy has the second greatest positive impact on customer satisfaction. Although this result is different from the findings of Munusamy Cselliah and Hor (2010), it is supported by Magoma et al. (2019). Especially, studies of Sulliman (2013), Vencataya et al. (2019) in other countries showed the impact of Empathy on customer satisfaction with high value of beta coefficient. It implies that customers in Vietnam may be more satisfied if they are taken care and their needs are understood.

Assurance also has positive significant impact on customer satisfaction. This is aligned with the results of Vencataya et al. (2019). In Vietnam, it is also in conformity with results of Tran and Nguyen (2020), as secured and safe information technology and services are important to banks' customers. In contrast, this result is different to findings of Sanjuq (2014) about insignificant effect of assurance on customer satisfaction in banking industry. For customers in Vietnam, it can be seen that this factor is also important, because of customers' low uncertainty avoidance preferences.

Tangibles also significant influence customer satisfaction. This result also strengthens the arguments of Tran et al. (2015) that Tangibles was the strongest factor as authors focused on deposit services of banks. However, this is contrast to findings that Tangibles had no significant impact on customer satisfaction in the study of Khan and Fasih (2014). Certainly, facilities, equipment, materials, and appearance of banks can also lead to customer satisfaction in Vietnam, as some of them prefer visiting banks' offices and branches to transact.

Responsiveness has significant influence on customer satisfaction. The result is different to the study of Munusamy et al. (2010) with no significant impact of Responsiveness on customer satisfaction; however, it is in line with Hussaien et al. (2020). It can be seen from the result that willingness to help and reacting to Vietnamese customers' feedback is also important to increase their satisfaction. If banks want to increase customers' satisfaction, they need to respond to customers' requests more quickly and effectively.

Conclusion

We examined the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in Vietnamese commercial banks. The five dimensions of SERVQUAL model—Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance, and Empathy—were used as independent variables and customer satisfaction as dependent variable. We also consolidated the SERVQUAL model fit in the context of Vietnamese commercial banks. We accepted all the hypotheses as all of them had a positive impact on customer satisfaction. Further, Reliability contributed most to satisfaction, followed by Empathy, Assurance, Tangibles and Responsiveness. Hence, Vietnamese commercial banks should concentrate on developing Reliability and remaining factors to improve customer satisfaction to be more competitive. It means the more outstanding quality of service is, the greater the customer satisfaction. In conclusion, service quality has a positive significant impact on customer satisfaction in Vietnamese commercial banks.

Implications for Managers

To improve Reliability, Vietnamese commercial banks should gain the bank's reputation by keeping accurate and reliable records (Pakurar et al. 2019). Moreover, Vietnamese commercial banks should keep up-to-date accurate information to improve customers' trust while processing the transaction by answering the customers' doubts and complaints (Nguyen et al. 2021). According to Tran et al. (2015), penetrating the customers' needs, making customers find confidence and safety when performing the bank's service is important. Therefore, Vietnamese commercial banks should also offer their staff training courses in communication skills and client care which also helps improve Empathy. Then, it is important to reinforce customer care, consultancy and have a better customer relationship management (Nguyen et al. 2021) as they wish to be respected by banks' staff (Munusamy et al. 2010). Moreover, banks' employees should attempt to remember the individual customer's name that makes each customer feel respectful.

Being appreciated and listened to meet personal needs make customers feel satisfied (Tran & Nguyen, 2020). Regarding Assurance, keeping secured online and offline transaction, confidential personal information and physical safety in the bank is necessary to increase customer satisfaction (Talavera 2020). The Tangibles and Responsiveness dimensions have the least impact on customer satisfaction. Banks are recommended to enhance service quality through feedback from customers and invest in physical facilities such as redesigning the appearance of offices, counters, and equipment.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

We only used questionnaires with a close-ended form of questions for data collection from the bank's customers, so there is lack of opinions from customers to reflect why they were satisfied or unsatisfied. Future study can combine quantitative and qualitative methods to have more detailed information. Second, there were only five dimensions in SERVQUAL; some more factors can be considered for inclusion in future studies such as compliance (Ali & Raza 2017), employees' competence and access (Pakurar et al. 2019).

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